

ISSUE OF PREGNANCY AFTER BARIATRIC OPERATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7309321>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 27th October 2022

Accepted: 06th November 2022

Online: 09th November 2022

KEY WORDS

overweight, metabolic syndrome, infertility, BMI, expected pregnancy, fertile, ideal weight.

ABSTRACT

Overweight and obesity are very common causes of infertility. Violation of the cycle, violation of ovulation, the development of polycystic ovaries are companions of obesity in women. These problems can be eliminated through the practice of bariatric surgery. It is also possible to get rid of excess weight and infertility.

Bariatrics (metabolic surgery) is a set of stomach and intestinal surgeries recommended by the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation for the treatment of obesity and diabetes (2018-2019 clinical recommendations).

Bariatric surgery, or morbid obesity surgery, is a general term used to describe

a variety of surgeries that make changes to the digestive system to promote long-term weight loss. Some weight loss surgeries are less invasive than others, and each has different recommendations and recovery times.

Fertility is not usually the main reason for weight loss surgery, but increasing the chances of conception is one of the main benefits. Characteristics of pregnancy after bariatric surgery. Scientific studies show that after bariatric surgery, menstrual disorders are eliminated in 100% of cases. Polycystic ovarian disease can be completely cured in 78% of cases. The overall probability of getting pregnant increases by 56%. In women, excess weight can prevent fertility: it causes hormonal imbalance, irregular ovulation and menstrual disorders. It can also reduce the success of assisted reproductive technology (such as in vitro fertilization or IVF). In men, excess weight can cause hormonal problems, erection and various health problems.

Likewise, being overweight during pregnancy can increase the risk of complications such as miscarriage, preeclampsia, gestational diabetes, fetal death, and the need for a cesarean section. Thus, weight loss after a bariatric procedure can help improve fertility. For example, a study conducted at the University of Utah (USA) showed that 70 of 98 women who underwent weight loss surgery began ovulating regularly a few months after the operation, that is, the ability to get pregnant was restored.

Pregnancy in bariatric patients is a little different. It does not come with significant weight gain. Sometimes the weight usually remains at the same level, and this can cause anxiety and panic in some gynecologists. Therefore, it must be observed by qualified professionals who are not afraid of it and know how it should be. We recommend contacting the Federal Scientific Center of Obstetrics and Gynecology. Kulakov, our bariatric

department has been working for a long time. Gynecologists of this center have extensive experience in managing pregnancy in bariatric patients. In addition, this center works according to the CHI system and can be accessed by any woman with a history of gastric bypass surgery.

Body weight is one of the many factors that affect your ability to conceive. Studies show that normal weight women are more likely to get pregnant and give birth. Thus, properly organized weight loss will ultimately help improve fertility. But what to expect if the goal is achieved through surgical methods?

Any weight loss operation is not easily tolerated by the body, so you should not try to conceive a child immediately after the procedure. To avoid possible complications, it is important to get your doctor's approval before trying to conceive. And pregnancy after weight loss surgery is different for everyone, depending on the type of surgery. We talk about pregnancy after bariatric procedures in general: what you need to know.

- Relationship between weight and fertility
- There is no ideal weight for conception.

A normal body weight for you depends largely on your height and other factors. Body mass index (BMI) is a measure of body fat based on a person's height and weight. Generally, a healthy BMI for adults is between 18.5 and 24.9, a BMI between 25 and 29 is considered overweight, and a BMI above 30 is considered obese. In women, excess weight can prevent fertility: it causes hormonal imbalance, irregular ovulation and menstrual disorders. It can also reduce the success of assisted reproductive

technology (such as in vitro fertilization or IVF).

In men, excess weight can cause hormonal problems, erection and various health problems. Likewise, being overweight during pregnancy can increase the risk of complications such as miscarriage, preeclampsia, gestational diabetes, fetal death, and the need for a cesarean section.

This, weight loss after a bariatric procedure can help improve fertility. For example, a study conducted at the University of Utah (USA) showed that 70 of 98 women who underwent weight loss surgery began ovulating regularly a few months after the operation, that is, the ability to get pregnant was restored. Weight loss surgery has been taken as a solution to fertility problems

Is pregnancy safe after weight loss surgery?

There are no contraindications for pregnancy after bariatric surgery - if there are no other pathologies. In fact, for many women, the chances of a healthy pregnancy improve significantly after weight loss surgery. Scientists say that weight loss after bariatric surgery can help reduce the risk of pregnancy-related complications, such as:

- ✓ Diabetes during pregnancy.
- ✓ High blood pressure.
- Early birth.
- ✓ Need for caesarean section.
- ✓ Postpartum bleeding.

When is the best time to plan pregnancy?

Allowing the weight to stabilize is recommended. It is worth planning a pregnancy 1-2 years after bariatric surgery, when the weight returns to normal and

reaches the plateau stage, that is, it stays in one place. If the weight is reduced, the patient has an energy deficit and pregnancy may become more difficult. Of course, if pregnancy occurred before the end of weight loss and a child was desired, then you do not have to give it up.

A University of Michigan study involved 1,850 women who became pregnant after bariatric surgery. Experts found that those who gave birth less than two years after the procedure had a higher risk of complications such as preterm birth, admission to the intensive care unit and low gestational age compared to those who waited four years. Relative fears that the child does not have enough of certain nutrients are unfounded. The fetus gets what it needs. And left only for my mother. In addition, all these deficiencies can be compensated by taking additional drugs orally or through the blood. But our practice shows that this is not required.

Conclusion. Special measures during and after pregnancy Malnutrition is a common complication in all people after weight loss surgery, regardless of gender or pregnancy plans. You should get regular checkups and work with a nutritionist to make sure your body is getting all the nutrients it needs to stay healthy.

Before conception, a nutritionist can conduct a series of tests to determine the need for supplements. During pregnancy, tests can be done monthly to monitor the intake and absorption of nutrients necessary for the health of the mother and fetus. In addition, the same examinations are recommended after delivery, especially if the mother plans to breastfeed the baby.

It's important to keep in touch with your doctor to make sure you're doing

everything you can to protect your health and your baby's development.

Most candidates for weight loss surgery must be pre-approved by a doctor, who

will only allow it if the patient meets certain conditions. Typically, patients with a BMI of 40 or higher or a dangerous diagnosis of overweight are referred.

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